

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Recommendations for diversification through the cultivation of undersowing in conventional wheat cultivation in the continental region

As part of a case study, the potential of extensification (wide seed rows, no plant protection products) and diversification (clover undersowing) to promote the natural bioregulation of mycotoxin-producing plant pathogenic fungi (especially *Fusarium*) was investigated in conventional wheat cultivation in the continental region. The aim was to identify management measures that enable fungicide reduction and nonetheless contribute to a decrease in fungal infestation and mycotoxin contamination by promoting antagonists. Key actors in this bioregulation are in particular fungivorous soil microarthropods (collembolans and mites). In the long term, a shift towards input-reduced management measures could help to positively affect soil health and biodiversity as well as resilience and sustainability of arable systems. Based on the results of

the study, we recommend to promote the cultivation of clover undersowing in conventional wheat production in the continental region in order to foster fungivorous soil fauna communities as antagonists of fungal plant pathogens. From an agro-ecological perspective, diversification increases soil biodiversity and promotes the ecosystem services it provides (e.g., bioregulation), while from an agro-economic perspective it has a positive legacy effect on crop revenue and profitability. However, attention must be paid to the composition of the clover species: suitable clover species are yellow clover and birdsfoot trefoil, unsuitable clover species are white and red clover, as they can serve as potential host plants for certain fungal plant pathogens such as some *Fusarium* species.

1. Single seed rows (left side) and wide seed rows (20 cm) (right side) in wheat cultivation on the experimental field.

2. Important antagonists of plant pathogenic fungi: the fungivorous collembolan species *Prosiotoma minuta*, *Sminthurinus aureus* and *Protaphorura armata* (from left to right).

KEYWORDS

Wheat cultivation, diversification, bioregulation, plant pathogenic fungi, soil fauna

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